

**FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN TEACHING THE SUBJECT OF FORMATION OF
MATHEMATICAL IMAGINATION IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR
IMPLEMENTATION**

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Annotation. Foreign experience in teaching the subject of formation of mathematical imagination in higher educational institutions and their implementation were discussed. On the basis of the conclusions reached, proposals have been developed.

Keywords: teacher-educator, preschool education, mathematics, education, mathematical imagination, method, methodology, knowledge, activity, thinking, understanding, game, learning process, result.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev analyzed this system in depth and drew attention to the smallest aspects that have been overlooked so far. It was found out that the improvement of state requirements for educational programs and educational plans of pre - school educational institutions today remains an urgent issue. The material and technical base of most preschool institutions does not meet the modern requirements. The indicator of coverage of children in preschool education is still low. In order to practically eliminate the existing problems, the resolution "on measures for further improvement of the preschool education system in 2017-2021" was adopted.

In order to make science more prosperous in our country, to educate our youth as the owner of deep knowledge, high spirituality and culture, to continue the intensive work we have started on the formation of a competitive economy and to raise it to a new, modern level, dear president of our country Sh.Mirziyoyev declared the year 2020 in our country as the Year of development of Science, Education and digital economy. In his remarks, the president said: "We must carry out extensive work on the Priority Development and reform of the spheres established in 2020. In particular, we need to bring the level of coverage of children of kindergarten age with preschool education to 60 percent in the current year..."¹. They stressed that in order to further increase the responsibility of personnel working in the field of preschool education, they gave several tasks and proposals.

The main place in the methodology of teaching mathematics to children of preschool age are questions that are asked as methodical methods. They can be reproductive-mnemonic, reproductive-cognition, reproductive-cognition. Bunch questions should be clear and concise. In the process of teaching, children should be a unit of reproductive and reproductive questions, depending on the age and the material to be studied. Questions provide for the development of children's thinking.

Questions to be asked to children can often be questions that apply to the group with the aim of gaining control. Often used Questions, These are questions that are called closed. There will be only one correct answer to them and they will be applied to check knowledge. Open questions that are asked during discussions are important in encouraging group activity and in analyzing the problems under consideration.

Let's look at the open questions.

Hypothetical questions. If ... if so, what would you think, would you laugh? They help children to imagine those or those situations, thinking process kuchaytiradi.

Questions that motivate thinking. How can we help in solving this problem?

Encouraging, supportive questions. It's very interesting, then what happened? They allow children to sympathize with their personal experiences and views.

Comment notification questions. You are ... on what do you think?" Such questions are used in telling children that their thoughts are important and interesting.

Interrogative questions. Why do you think that? This question, which is given with memorization, helps them to think deeply about their thoughts and analyze their explanations.

Explanatory, generalizing questions. You are ... if I say that you think, will I be right? Summarizing what the child says and checking whether he understands it correctly, encourages others to think about how they will react to this idea.

Questions of consent. Many ... do you agree that it is? Such questions can be asked to encourage discussion. Or, at the end of the discussion, did we finish this part? questions like will be given to get permission to move to the next topic.

Try to remember not to use secondary questions, for example, quot; X - right, is it? Such questions slow down the activity of the child. Do not ask too many questions in one zum and do not use two-meaning questions.

With the question, it is necessary not to force children to be protected, there must be an opportunity to choose in them and create this opportunity themselves. They can be as follows:

- reproductive-mnemonic (for example: what is it? What color is the flag? How is this figura called?);

- reproductive-know (for example: how many cubes will there be if I put one more in the regiment? Which number is larger (smaller): 9 or 7?);

- produktiv-know (for example: what should be done so that the paws are equal? How do we solve this task? How to determine what the red flag is on the account?).

It is necessary not to ask too many questions in one zum and not to use two-meaning questions. Questions in children faollashtirad acceptance, memory, thinking, speech. In the formation of elementary mathematical representations, a lot of complex questions are used, mainly from simple to complex, which are aimed at highlighting the exact signs, properties, results of practical action of subjects, requiring the use of links, relationships, connections, their explanation and justification, simple proof.

More such questions are asked by the educator either after the demonstration of the sample, or after the child has completed the assignment. For example, when children have two equal parts of a paper rectifier, they are asked: "What did you do? How is this part called? Why can each of these two parts be called half? What form was formed from the part? How to prove that a square is formed? What to do to divide the rectifier into four equal parts?"

As a methodological method, we distinguish some basic requirements that are imposed on the questions of the educator: accuracy, accuracy, logical sequence, variety of formulations, the optimal ratio of reproductive and productive questions in accordance with the age of the children of the material being studied, the fact that the questions arouse, develop, think, analyze, compare, compare, generalize the child's thinking, the, it is necessary to tell the answer slowly and avoid similar questions, it is necessary to skillfully use additional questions. It is necessary to consider questions as an effective means of learning activity in the development of children's elementary mathematical imagination, as well as to allow them to think over the answer. It is necessary to teach children to formulate questions independently. With the use of didactic material in a specific situation, the educator offers them to put questions about the number of subjects, their size, shape, methods of measurement. We will indicate the methodological requirements for children's answers:

- be short or complete questions depending on the question harakter;
- independent and understood; correct, accurate, grammatically correct.

When compiling tasks in the form of the use of the option of base words and phrases, it is also necessary to pay attention to the amount of tasks to be solved by supporting interactive methods. The application of these methods ensures the development of children's thinking skills, mastering the material at a high level of quality.

The educator should choose a suitable one of these methods, depending on the topic of the lesson. When using interactive methods in training, it is recommended to follow the following methodological recommendations:

- prepare a place to work, create comfortable conditions for children, prepare materials for creative work in advance;
- to have a serious attitude to the process and regulation, to respect the freedom of speech of children;
- to pay serious attention to the division of children into groups, to attract all to work, to facilitate the preparation of Ruhan, to provide exercises in this regard, constant incentives for their active participation in the work, to create an opportunity for the self-expression of the child;
- to achieve that there are not many children in the group when using interactive methods, the composition consists of 4-6 people, to work effectively in small groups, to listen to everyone, to allow each group to come up with a statement of the problem. Interactive methods provide for a constant interaction between the educator and the child. These methods of improper application of them reduce the effectiveness or that

it causes the appearance of a misconception about.

In pedagogy, the system of questions and answers of children is called Conversation. The method of conversation with the help of well-thought-out questions implies a conversation between the educator and the child, which leads to the acquisition of new concepts of their independent thinking. When using it, methods of putting questions, discussing the answers and feedback of children, forming conclusions, correcting answers are used.

During the conversation, the educator pays special attention to the correct use of mathematical terms by children, speech literacy. This will be followed by various explanations and their acceptance will be clarified. For example, if the educator teaches children to check geometric figurestiradi, take the figure qo'with your left hand and show the sides of the square (for example: a right triangle, a triangle). Or another example, when the educator teaches children to measure, puts a measure, then shows and tells how to calculate the measure.

As children grow older, the problematic questions and cases that are given to them also increase in size. The occurrence of a problematic situation: the connection between the proof and the result is not opened at once, gradually. In this the question arises: What is it? (for example, we drop different objects into the water: one crashes, the other does not sink); after describing some parts of the material, the child must guess (for example, melting ice, experimenting with hot water, solving the issue); the use of such words as " sometimes", " some", " only in some cases " serves as signs of specific cognition; in order to understand the argument, it is necessary to compare it with other facts, to create a system of discussion, that is, to carry out certain mental operations (for example, to make different measurements, to calculate with a group).

The effect can be achieved with the help of problematic assignments, proceeding from the specific situation and the essence of the problem posed by the problem method. Mastering the materials, tasks and creating a problematic situation in the solution of exercises and issues will come to hand. In it, small groups are formed, educational materials are given to groups separately. Once the final conclusions and solutions are found, the topics will be shared among the groups.

Any pedagogical technology that is being applied to the educational process, regardless of whether its components are passed through the content of the course, the educational program, textbooks or pedagogical activity, is required to develop the free and creative activity of the child. Methods of teaching are the main part of the educational process, without which it is impossible to carry out pedagogical activity. Transfer and reception of knowledge is divided into expressive, visual and practical ways by word, depending on the harakter. In mastering the content of the topics of the training session, explanatory-illustrative, reproductive, problematic statement, private search or euristic and semi-research methods are used.

In practical ways, work is carried out to put the task (goal), plan the method of its implementation, manage the execution process, analyze it, determine the cause of the shortcomings, correct and make changes to the process of the training session in order to achieve

the goal in full. In carrying out practical exercises, children actively observe their future actions, listen to themselves and interpret the upcoming events.

The free-thinking method is devoted to illustrations, photo shoots and their discussion. The purpose of this lesson is to expand the knowledge circle, worldview of children, to introduce them to painting, photography, books, to acquire their knowledge and interest, to acquire new knowledge by applying the previously acquired knowledge, skills and skills in new situations.

The assignment should be as follows: not to be large in size, but to be meaningful, focused on assimilation, obscurity, repetition, thinking, practical; to be simple and understandable in relation to what is done in the group; to be connected with the observations and thoughts of children, especially in the formation of examples and sentences, in the conduct of practical work; to be given; it is necessary to individualize taking into account the children's preparation and opportunities: the educator must check the homework in the TR time to ensure the discipline and responsibility of the children.

In the place of the conclusion, it should be said that in our country, attention is paid to the educational system at the level of state policy mathematical activity of Educators was grown in various conditions: in theatrical activity, in construction-building games, in activity centers. Knowledge of the strengths of the manifestation in children is important not only for analysis, but also allows to determine in them the prospects for further professional selection, stimulation of mathematical abilities. It is necessary to take into account the demonstrated ability of the child not only to develop them, but also to direct his talent to the appropriate flow. experiments have shown that games and interactive methods promote the development of children's mathematical abilities, create conditions for obtaining a wide range of goals in mathematics and the accumulation of a reserve of mathematical impressions, provide the basis for the successful solution of the tasks of "state requirements for the development of children of Primary and preschool age".

REFERENCES

1. Ravshanbek, J. (2022). CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM, ITS BASIC PRINCIPLES AND FEATURES. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnali*, 1(4), 304-309.
2. O'G'Li, J. R. M. (2022). METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDEPENDENT STUDY OF STUDENTS IN THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM. *Ta'lim fidoyilari*, 25(5), 93-97.
3. Inomovna, K. N. (2022). Principles of Educational Psychology and Pedagogy. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 5, 191-193.
4. Botirova, M., & Seytsaliyeva, I. (2021). Formation of the Ability of Primary School Students to Evaluate and Diagnose the Future Professional Activity of the Child. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(4), 68-70.
5. Madgafurova, D. (2022). THE ESSENCE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION AND ITS ROLE IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(06), 68-71.

6. Madgafurova, D. (2022). INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF TEACHERS IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(06), 61-64.
7. Ohunovna, M. D. (2022). Ways to Teach Students to Independent, Creative Thinking Through Practical Activities. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 6, 1-4.
8. Ahunovna, M. D. (2022). The Role of Reading in the Development of Children's Psyche in Early Childhood.
9. Ahunovna, M. D. (2022). The Role of Reading in the Development of Children's Psyche in Early Childhood. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL ON ORANGE TECHNOLOGY*, 4(01), 38-40.
10. Abdurashidov, A. A. (2019). Methodology of formation skills of entrepreneurship among students through the national crafts. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences-Great Britain*, 7(7), 41.
11. Abdurashidov, A. (2020). Pedagogical Technology Used To Determine And Increase The Effectiveness Of Development Of Entrepreneurship In Students Through National Crafts. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 13658-13664.
12. Abdurashidov, A. (2020). DEVELOPMENT OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN STUDENTS THROUGH NATIONAL CRAFTS, TAKING ADVANTAGE OF PEDAGOGICAL FACILITIES. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(7), 1573-1576.
13. Adxam, Z. (2021). Pedagogical Factors in Forming a Sense of Homeland Based on National and Universal Values in Primary School Students. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 17, 284-286.
14. Ziyayev, A. N. (2022). PRIMARY EDUCATION AND AESTHETIC SENSE TRAINING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 16(06), 62-64.
15. Ziyayev, A. N. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE USE OF EDUCATIONAL VALUES IN THE SPIRITUAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 16(06), 86-88.
16. Nurmatova, M. (2021). Family economy: Sources of income and types of costs. *Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management*, 11(11), 69-73.
17. Нурматова, М. И. (2022). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОПИСАНИЕ ПОНЯТИЯ "ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ КОМПЕНСАЦИЯ". In *СОВРЕМЕННАЯ НАУКА: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ* (pp. 147-148).
18. Нурматова, М. (2021). Оила иқтисоди ва уни юритишга оид компетенциялар. *Общество и инновации*, 2(11/S), 323-329.
19. Mirzaeva, F., Mirsagatova, N., Abdullaeva, O., Rejemetova, I., & Raximova, F. (2020). IMPROVING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS BASED ON A PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(6), 8919-8926.

20. Muhammadjanovna, R. F. (2022). THE SYSTEM OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE EDUCATORS THROUGH PERSONCENTERED EDUCATION. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 7, 75-77.
21. Muhammadjonovna, R. F. (2021). Improvement Of The System Of Formation And Development Of Creative Activity Of Future Educators On The Basis Of PersonalityOriented Education. *Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3, 32-36.
22. Mukhammadjonovna, R. F. (2021). Pedagogical and psychological features of the formation of the creative activity of future teachers through personality-oriented education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(4), 1053-1056.
23. Raximova, F. M. (2021). PROBLEMS OF ESTABLISHING AND STRENGTHENING THE MATERIAL BASE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (4-7), 51-56.
24. Зокиров, М. А. (2021). ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА ТАЯНЧ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ АСОСИДА ИЖТИМОЙ ФАОЛЛИКНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК АСОСЛАРИ. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 2(4), 491-197.
25. Guzal, N. (2022). МАКТАБГАЧА КАТТА YOSHDAГИ BOLALARDA IJTIMOЙ ONGNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(5), 35-39.
26. Guzal, N. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(5), 40-46.
27. Malikovna, N. G. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE USE OF MASS MEDIA FOR THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(06), 52-57.
28. Guzal, N. (2022). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN PRESCHOOL-ADULT CHILDREN. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(5), 47-51.
29. Malikovna, N. G. (2022). MODERN APPROACHES TO THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM OF PRESCHOOL ORGANIZATIONS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(06), 76-81.
30. Anvarovna, S. N., Bahadirovna, K. D., & Gapparovna, I. S. (2022). PSYCHOLOGY OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 59-65.
31. Halimova, K. M. (2021). Adaptation of Teachers and Psychologists to Specific Life. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 17, 202-203.
32. Каримова, М. Х., & Эргашева, М. (2021). ПЕДАГОГ ШАХСИ ВА УНИНГ ҲАЁТИЙ ВАЗИЯТЛАРГА МОСЛАШИШ ТАЛАБЛАРИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(CSPI conference 1), 1298-1302.

33. Yuldashev, D., Karabayev, H., & Shodiyeva, G. (2021, June). FORMS AND TYPES OF ORGANIZATION OF EDUCATION ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES. In Euro-Asia Conferences (pp. 22-24).
34. YULDASHEV, D., & SOLIYEVA, G. (2022). Organizing Educational Processes On The Basis Of Information Technology. *Procedia of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 36-38.
35. Yuldashev, D. (2022). Socialized Educational System. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 254-256.
36. Otakoziyevich, Y. M., & Mamurovich, Y. D. (2022). TEMPERING THE WILL QUALITIES OF JUNIOR SCHOOL AGE STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(03), 16-21.
37. Toshmatova, Z. J. (2021). Interaction of kindergarten and family in modern conditions. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(4), 853-860.
38. Rakhmonov, E. A. (2021). The effect of the demographic situation on social problems in fergana valley. *ACADEMICIA: AN INTERNATIONAL MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH JOURNAL*, 11(2), 453-456.
39. Раҳмонов, Э. А. (2020). ЎЗБЕКИСТОН МУСТАҚИЛЛИКА ЭРИШИШ АРАФАСИДА ИЖТИМОЙ МУАММОЛАР ВА УНИ ҲАЛ ЭТИШ ЙЎЛИДАГИ ТАРИХИЙ ОДИМЛАР (ФАРҶОНА ВОДИЙСИ МИСОЛИДА). *Academic research in educational sciences*, (4), 142-151.
40. Rakhmonov, E. (2021, August). THE IMPORTANCE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN PROVIDING YOUTH EMPLOYMENT IN UZBEKISTAN (Example of Fergana region): <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1297>. In *RESEARCH SUPPORT CENTER CONFERENCES* (No. 18.05).
41. Ахмедова, Р. М., & Адиллов, Ф. А. (2016). Подготовка специалистов в отрасли ремесленного производства в 20-х годах XX века. *Учёный XXI века*, (5-4 (18)), 62-64.
42. Mukimovna, A. R. (2020, December). HISTORY OF CHILDREN'S SANATORIUM RESORTS IN UZBEKISTAN (1930-1953). In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 9, No. 1, pp. 311-314).
43. Ахмедова, Р. (2020). ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ДАСТЛАБКИ ШИФО МАСКАНЛАРИНИНГ ВУЖУДГА КЕЛИШИ (ФАРҶОНА ВОДИЙСИ МИСОЛИДА). *ВЗГЛЯД В ПРОШЛОЕ*, (SI-1№ 1).
44. Азизхонова, М., & Қобилова, Э. (2022). ЁШЛАРНИ МУСИҚИЙ МАДАНИЯТИ ВА МАЪНАВИЯТНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШДА МУСИҚИЙ ТАРБИЯНИНГ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(1), 51-57.
45. Қобилова, Э. Б. (2022). ФОРМИРОВАТЬ ДУХОВНОЕ МИРОВОЗЗРЕНИЕ ПОДРАСТАЮЩЕГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ ЧЕРЕЗ ФОЛЬКЛОРА ЖАНРА. *Oriental Art and Culture*, 3(1), 291-295.